

Figure 5. Effect of inflammatory mediators (IM) on DRGs nerve endings. (a) Treatment and assays timeline. Axons were treated with inflammatory mediators or vehicle at DIV five and recorded at DIV six or DIV8. (b)–(c) Representative traces of responsive neurons. Y axes represents fluorescence normalized to somal KCl response. (d) Percentage of response normalized to Did+ and somal KCl responsive cells. Mean \pm SEM. Statistical analysis two-tailed Mann-Whitney U. (e)–(h) Responses to capsaicin and menthol, menthol and AITC or capsaicin and AITC normalized to KCl response in the soma. (i) Size of the response normalized to somal KCl response. Mean \pm SEM, every dot represents a cell. Statistical analysis two-tailed Mann-Whitney U. $N=6$ animals, three males and three females; $n \geq 3$ coverslips per animal; total number of crossing neurons=3018.

Neuropathic sensitization and resolution of peripheral ends

Exposure of nociceptor primary cultures to paclitaxel for 24 h produced a significant increase in neuronal activity that peaked 48 h after removal of the chemotherapeutic drug and mitigated 96 h after exposure.²⁸ Here, we questioned if a similar sensitization-resolution occurs when the drug is applied onto axonal endings. To investigate the impact of the drug on the peripheral ends, we

exposed them to 1 μ M paclitaxel (PTX) or vehicle (DMSO 0.04%) for 24 h (DIV6, Table S3). PTX was removed, and neuronal functionality was recorded 48 (DIV8) and 96 h (DIV10) after drug removal (Figure 6(a)). As exhibited in Figure S8, paclitaxel reversibly reduced axonal density, being the strongest effect just after treatment and fully resolving 96 h post-treatment.

Functional analysis revealed that 40 mM KCl in the axonal compartment evoked activity in 20% of neurons at DIV 8 and 10. Paclitaxel did not significantly affect the percentage of